

CULTURAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS: COMMUNICATION PRACTICES AND INTERNATIONAL APPROACHES.

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Annotation. The field of intercultural communication has been criticized for failing to produce studies which focus on actual practices of communication, especially of intercultural encounters. The framework responds to specific research questions, addresses particular kinds of intellectual problems, includes five investigative modes, and uses a special set of concepts. In this essay, each of the modes is discussed as analytically distinct, yet as complementary to the others, including theoretical, descriptive, interpretive, comparative, and critical analyses. Special attention is given to the interpretive mode and to intercultural interactions as a site for the application and development of cultural discourse analysis.

Keywords: *cultural discourse; ethnography of communication; communication code*

Studies of intercultural communication have sought recently to bring together two important kinds of insights, the cultural shaping of communication practices including its nonverbal features (e.g., Milburn, 2000; Scollo, 2004; Wilkins, 2005), competence (Witteborn, 2003), and the interactional dynamics that occur among culturally shaped communication practices (e.g., Bailey, 2000). This essay is an explication of one particular shaped approach for creating these insights, cultural discourse analysis (Cu DA).¹Cultural discourse analysis raises the general question: how is communication shaped as a cultural practice? Specific questions may focus upon acts, events, and styles of communication that people use when conducting their everyday lives, including their practical rhetorical arts.¹Whatever the particular phenomena of concern, the inquiry explores what people in particular places make of communication when practiced in their own way, when understood through their own terms, through their own explanations. How is communication conducted, conceived and evaluated in this place among these people? Investigations designed to respond to these questions help us understand the local shapes and forms communication takes such as a Chinese version of “pure talk”(Garrett, 1993), loathing the “sucker” role in Israel (Bloch, 2003), a Puerto Rican view of time (Milburn, 2000, 2002), or suppressing an East Asian identity in specific interactional contexts (Hastings, 2000). Investigations also can tackle the complexities of intercultural interactions between racial, ethnic, and national styles of engagement² A second, related question asks: what system of symbolic meanings or what cultural commentary is imminent in practices of communication? When people are engaged in communication, what significance and meaning does it have for them? When addressed, analyses delve into the deep meanings that are active in communication practices, and how these are part of a practical way of living. Inquiry proceeds in order to hear the rich symbolic texture, the presumed view of the symbolic world that is presumed in order to communicate in this way. These general research questions, about the cultural nature and the meanings of communication, are based upon the view that communication both presumes and

¹ Carbaugh, D. (1988a). Talking American: Cultural discourses on DONAHUE. Norwood, NJ: Ablex. Carbaugh, D. (1988b). Comments on “culture” in communication inquiry. *Communication Reports*, 1

² Carbaugh, D. (2005). *Cultures in conversation*. New York & London: Lawrence Erlbaum & Associates. Carbaugh, D. (2007). A cultural discourse theory of emotion. Paper presented at the Eastern Communication Association, Providence, Rhode Island.

constitutes social realities; and further, that as people communicate, so they engage in a meta-cultural commentary, that is, they (and we) say things explicitly and implicitly about who they are, how they are related to each other, how they feel, what they are doing, and how they are situated in the nature of things. These latter concerns about identity, relationships, emotions, actions, and dwelling, respectively, are central concepts in cultural discourse analysis, and are elaborated below.

Cultural discourse analysis is a particular way of investigating communication ethnographically. It is indebted to the Hymesian program of work³ while standing at the juncture of the theories of cultural communication⁴ and communication codes⁵. The program of work 168 D. Carbaugh focuses inquiries on communication as a practice and culture as emergent in practices; special attention is given to interpreting the deeply meaningful commentary that is intelligible to participants as part of their ongoing social life. The concept, cultural discourse, has therefore been used systematically to organize ways of understanding how culture is an integral part, and a product of discourse systems. The concept has been focused from the beginning on the relationship between discourses of personhood and communication, with these discourses being understood, like intercultural interactions, to be multidimensional, polysemic, deeply situated, and complex functional accomplishments⁶. Focused on discursive dynamics, cultural discourse has been defined as a historically transmitted expressive system of communication practices, of acts, events, and styles, which are composed of specific symbols, symbolic forms, norms and their meanings⁷. How analysts can describe, and then subsequently interpret communication practices, that is, how analysts identify the cultural features of acts, events, and styles of communication, is the focus of what follows.

Cultural discourse analysis treats meaning as an ongoing commentary that is immanent in actual communication practices. In other words, as people communicate with each other, they are saying things literally about the specific subject being discussed, but they are also saying things culturally, about who they are, how they are related, what they are doing together, how they feel about what is going on, and about the nature of things. These cultural meanings—about personhood, relationships, action, emotion, and dwelling, respectively—are formulated in cultural discourse analyses as “radiant of cultural meaning” or “hubs of cultural meaning” which are active in communication practice. We know from the ethnographic literature about communication that these radiant and hubs are actively a part of communication practices. It is the rendering of these interactional radiant or semantic hubs, the explication of this ongoing meta-cultural commentary, which is the task of interpretive analysis. The radiant discussed below provide a way of structuring the interpretive analysis. The objective is to render an enriched reading of the meanings in a way that does not simply replicate and parrot what has been said already by participants, but creates a productive portrait of the meaningfulness of the practice to participants. In my experience, the interpretive account is successful if participants say something like “That’s right, that’s how we do things, but I hadn’t thought of it quite like that before”⁸ Interpretive analysis is then both replicative of participants’ meanings, that is, it does not violate their sense of themselves, and it is also partially creative, for it puts their practice in a somewhat different semantic light.

³ Hymes, 1972; Philipsen & Carbaugh, 1986

⁴ Philipsen, 1987, 2002

⁵ Philipsen, 1997; Philipsen, Coutu & Covarrubias, 2005

⁶ Carbaugh, D. (1988a). *Talking American: Cultural discourses on DONAHUE*. Norwood, NJ: Ablex. Carbaugh, D. (1988b). Comments on “culture” in communication inquiry. *CommunicationReports*, 1

⁷ Carbaugh, D., Gibson, T., & Milburn, T. A. (1997). A view of communication and culture: Scenes in an ethnic cultural center and private college. In B. Kovacic (Ed.), *Emerging theories of human communication*

⁸ Carbaugh, D. (1989/1990). The critical voice in ethnography of communication research. *Research on Language and Social Interaction*, 23(1989/1990), 261–282

Cultural radiant of meaning have been explicated in various prior works mentioned throughout this report. The ideas, then, are not declared here in the abstract, but derive from a body of descriptive and interpretive work. For sake of this discussion, I will briefly discuss each of the five radiant of meaning. Each suggests a question to ask about the meaning of a discursive practice to participants. Each hub implicates the others, even if all are not always highly salient.

The above framework provides a way of designing cultural research of discourses. It suggests a wide range of questions, proposes modes of inquiry for responding to those questions, provides a specific interpretive stance for discourse analysis, with a special set of concepts. When designing a study, then, the analyst can adopt or create a specific theoretical, descriptive, and interpretive approach to it that serves its purposes.

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